

Strategy to Enhance Organizational Performance Through A New Functional Management Initiative at Bor Penunjang Migas

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ABSTRACT: Bor Penunjang Migas (BPM) is a rig contractor that operates about 47 drilling rigs across Indonesia. Besides rigs, BPM has a small number of associated drilling services (non-rig), such as directional drilling, cementing, drilling fluid, casing running, coring services, etc. Historically, BPM has rented out rig and non-rig equipment separately. However, the market for non-rig services is less mature than rig services. Despite accounting for less than 10% of BPM's productive assets, non-rig services contribute over 20% of the company's revenue and consistently achieve a net profit margin (NPM) exceeding 15%, in contrast to the approximately 5% NPM from rigs.

Currently, there is massive ramping up of drilling activities in Indonesia; therefore, BPM expects significant growth in both revenue and profit. Given the operational and financial performance, asset structure, and organizational capabilities, BPM is redefining its business strategy to emphasize enhancing non-rig services alongside its core rig offerings. To improve marketing and asset productivity, the company plans to offer end-to-end integrated drilling services by bundling rig and non-rig offerings. This marks BPM's strategic transformation from a conventional rig contractor to an integrated drilling service provider.

This paper discusses the change process behind this new strategic direction, including the applied change model, key behaviours required for successful transformation, core elements to be addressed, and the expected benefits of implementing the new initiative.

KEYWORDS: Change Management, Integrated Drilling Services, Leading the Change.

INTRODUCTION

Oil production remains strategically essential in the Indonesian national economy. Crude oil is an energy source for electricity generation and transportation and is a significant portion of Indonesia's industrial infrastructure. Therefore, production continuously increases to reduce dependence on crude oil imports (Fitnawan et al., 2021). Indonesia seeks to achieve the production target of 1 million barrels of oil per day (MMBOPD) and 12 billion standard cubic feet of gas per day (BSCFD) by 2030. Although the current average national oil production is 650 thousand barrels per day (BOPD), the government is optimistic that these targets can be achieved (BPM, 2022). One of the strategies to support this government mission is to drill more wells, expecting additional oil from the new wells. In 2021, the country drilled 616 wells, which increased to around 1000 wells in 2023 and will continue to increase by 30% yearly. As a drilling contractor in Indonesia, BPM is expected to reap the benefit of ramped-up drilling activities.

BPM COMPANY PROFILE

BPM was founded in 2008, renting drilling rigs to clients to conduct drilling exploration and development wells of oil, gas, and geothermal resources (Arifin & Chaerudin, 2020).

A. Organization Structure

Its organizational structure is shown in the following organigram, led by a Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and eight functions report directly to the CEO, three Directors, four Vice Presidents and Corporate Secretary. They are Operation, Marketing and Development, Business Support including Finance, Supply Change, Audit, HSSEQ and Human Capital.

Figure 1. Organizational Structure

B. Scope of Services and Assets

BPM strives to maintain operational excellence to ensure the sustainability of the company. As drilling contractor, it provides rig service as primary scope and other associated drilling services as secondary.

Figure 2. Rig Unit and Non-Rig Operated by Bor Penunjang Migas

BPM owns 45 onshore rigs with power capacity between 150 - 2000 HP and operates two offshore workover rigs with a capacity of 550 HP (BPM, 2021). Associated drilling (non-rig) services include directional drilling, cementing and pumping, drilling fluid and completion fluid, casing running, fishing and coring, H2S monitoring, water pump, aerated drilling, real-time monitoring, geomechanics, workover display parameter recorder, centrifuge, cutting dryer, mud cooler, mud containment, mud logging unit. The asset allocation ratio is 90% for rig and 10% for non-rig equipment.

C. Operation and Financial Performance

Until 2021, operational performance from all company assets, rig and non-rig as revenue generators, varied (see Figure 3). The operational performance represented asset productivity, a 60% average in the last six years (BPM, 2021).

Figure 3. Operational Performance on Annual Report (2021)

BPM's revenue is proportional to asset productivity. Figure 3 depicts the main factor that affected this low productivity in 2019: declining drilling activities due to triple economic shock (pandemic-low oil price-global recession). In 2021, revenue started increasing after ramping up drilling activities. This was triggered by the Indonesian government's proclaimed 1-million-barrel oil production per day.

Figure 4. Revenue YoY on Annual Report (2021)

Figure 4 depicts the revenue composition along last six-year, shows that non-rig services contributed more percentage of revenue compared to rig service. Accordingly, non-rig services generated more percentage of net-profit-margin (NPM).

Figure 5. Rig vs Non-Rig Profit on Annual Report (2021)

Better NPM of non-rig services because Cost of Goods Sold (COGS) from these streams lower than COGS of rig services (see Figure 5).

BUSINESS ISSUE

Nowadays, BPM is recognized as a rig contractor that mainly rents drilling rigs for clients. More than 90% of the company's resources are supporting rig operations. Unfortunately, this rig business, which spends the majority of its workforce and investment, contributes only 78% of total revenue and gives less than 70% of the company's net profit. Whilst non-rig services are only supported by 10% of the company's resources, they can obtain 22% revenue and earn 30% net profit. In addition, the company's asset productivity of 60% was considered low in the last six years.

Considering the above phenomena, BPM has to introduce a new business strategy, prioritizing non-rig streams and transforming into an integrated drilling company:

- The first step is to develop the company's capability and expand the market for non-rig services. This service is more profitable than the rig.

- Secondly, BPM promotes integrated drilling services: rig and its associated (non-rig) services in one package. Rather than offering rig rental in stand-alone service, BPM could offer rig and other non-rig services in bundling (see Figure 6), then deliver a completed well, ready to produce to the client. More precisely, BPM must promote an end-to-end drilling service where the company is operating its own rig, and expected asset productivity will be improved. BPM's objective is to grow double in 2024, along with Indonesia's massive ramp-up of drilling activities.

Figure 6. Business Transformation for BPM to Grow

LITERATURE REVIEW

PROBLEM EXPLORATION

Implementation of a new business strategy necessitates a strategic approach. Below are BPM's grand strategic analysis and SWOT analysis before transformation.

Product-market strategy yields a set of criteria for considering business alignment with a particular business target (Ansoff, 1957, p.124). Four strategies (see Table 1) are formulated, emphasizing growth expectations and objectives (Watts et al., 1998).

Table 1. Ansoff Corporate Strategy (cited in, Watts et al., 1998)

	Current Products	New
Current Markets	Market Penetration	Product Development
New Markets	Market Development	Diversification

Diversification is an expansion strategy that redefines the business by developing new products or expanding the market to enhance competitive advantage. Diversification strategies have proven to generate improved organizational performance in terms of return on assets (ROA) and return on investment (ROI). Furthermore, diversification leads the organization to revenue growth and profitability (Oladimeji & Itohowo, 2019). BPM's business expansion is classified as diversification, which includes several elements as part of its diversification strategy to transform into an integrated drilling service provider.

The elements to change are organization structure, technology/ equipment, people capability and tasks/ business process. The success of this change relies on long-term investment strategies, partnerships, and acquiring new equipment. Given the scale of this strategic shift, BPM recognizes the importance of careful and efficient planning to achieve positive outcomes.

Before further process, BPM performs Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis to map its current business situation. SWOT analysis is the traditional method used to gain insights into achieving the desired alignment (Valentin, 2001). The process of implementing a strategic direction using the SWOT analysis tool begins with an assessment of external environmental Opportunities and Threats. Following this, the SWOT analysis will evaluate the internal Strengths and Weaknesses of the company to define its competitive advantages compared to rival firms (Daft, 2021, p.50).

Then, the change in integrated drilling operations refers to integrating services, disciplines, people, organizations, work processes, and information-communication technology to improve work efficiency. In short, integrated drilling is a collaboration focusing on healthy delivery "safer, faster, cheaper". BPM will provide full-cycle, well-drilling services spanning from the initial stages to project completion, resulting in cost-efficiency and shorter operational timelines.

BPM will be exposed to several previously unexplored sectors through the planned initiative business strategy. Adding service goods will result in a major scale shift in BPM's business operations. Therefore, this research tries to plan strategic change to optimize the chance for success. Furthermore, the strategic change management of BPM demands thorough preparation and an implementation timeline to assess and stabilize the new changes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integrated drilling management emphasizes all technical and non-technical factors that influence operational outcomes. Integrated project management is conducted to predict time, budget, scope, collaboration, and the required duration. Hence, drilling projects encompass various scopes of management, including time, cost, quality, risk, communications, procurement, and stakeholder management (Omosebi et al., 2014). Integrated drilling operations are also defined as transforming work processes to achieve improved decision-making, remote control over processes and equipment, and relocating functions and personnel to remote installations or onshore facilities (Rosendahl et al., 2012).

Drilling projects were conservatively executed with separate contracts for rig and non-rig (oilfield) services and other support services. Thus, integrated drilling services combine drilling rig and oilfield services management, unified within a project (bundling scheme) and operated by a single centralized management (companies).

As a benchmark, ADNOC Drilling is currently making efforts to integrate drilling project management. ADNOC is implementing a change strategy by selling shares, joint ventures, commercial partnerships, and acquisitions. Partnerships are aligned with the required capabilities and expertise. ADNOC aims to create integrated services with competitive and efficient operations while ensuring all partners benefit from this collaboration (Moeller & Desai, 2021a, 2021b).

A. Theory of Project Management

In the context of organizational change, project management is the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to activities supporting the change initiative's success. Project management focuses on planning, executing, monitoring, and controlling the change project from inception to completion, including managing limited resources such as time, money, equipment, and personnel. Project management is also integrated with leadership, which drives the initiation of change and is interlinked with change management (Hornstein, 2015).

B. Theory of Change Management

Change management involves a methodical approach to executing adjustments within a company. The primary purpose is to shift the organization from its old, inflexible operational procedures to embracing new ways associated with its future goals (Dawson, 2014). Change management facilitates sensemaking across all organizational parts within change projects. It serves various

functions, including analyzing the impacts, risks, and obstacles during the change process (Fusch et al., 2020). According to Bassioni et al. (2005), strategic plan management is driven by factors of people management, intellectual capital management, partnership and suppliers management, resources management, and risk management.

It is essential to plan change because change aversion is often encountered at the individual level during the process. Aversion occurs because individuals may experience a fear of the unknown, discomfort over the potential loss of control, or simply unfamiliarity with the desired organizational initiation (Hubbart, 2023). For success to occur, an organization must analyze all potential needs that may become problems or crises during change. Consequently, managers formulate ideas and needs simultaneously, transforming them into materials and equipment for implementation, constituting organizational steps encompassing various activities, timelines, and resources (Cummings & Worley, 2015, p.484-487).

ADKAR Model: Success in change is not solely about having an outstanding vision, the best solutions, or the executed projects. The key to successful change is understanding and facilitating change at the individual level (Hiatt, 2006, p.1-2). The ADKAR model comprises five elements represented by an acronym to facilitate efficient recall and explanation. These five foundational elements of ADKAR constitute a sequential lifecycle, progressing from one stage to the next. According to Hiatt (2006, p.1-2), the definitions of these five elements are Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement.

Kotter 8-Steps Leading Change: Organizations often fail to transform effectively due to a lack of understanding of the complexities and challenges involved in the change process. Many organizations may change superficially or only in appearance without addressing fundamental aspects. Such failures are commonly attributed to eight prevalent mistakes. According to Kotter (1995), these mistakes can be anticipated and mitigated through the following eight steps: establishing a sense of urgency, forming a guiding coalition, creating a vision, communicating the vision, empowering others to act on the vision, planning for and creating short-term wins, consolidating improvements and producing more change, and institutionalizing new approaches.

McKinsey 7S Model: The 7S Framework is introduced as a paradigm for organizational effectiveness. This framework acts as a roadmap for organizations attempting to implement transformation. The seven aspects of this framework are considered vital and linked. Organizations must address all seven factors to accomplish sustainable change. The seven components of the 7S framework include strategy, structure, system, staff, style, skills and shared values.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

After doing a pros and cons analysis among the three change models, the ADKAR model is chosen as the primary framework and considered more appropriate for this study as it provides a framework for monitoring change management progress. This is supported by survey research based on the construction of each ADKAR element. In contrast, Kotter's (1995) 'Leading Change' model focuses on steps that are challenging to measure to objectively assess overall change management progress. The McKinsey 7S Framework (Peters & Waterman, 2012) focuses on seven interrelated organizational elements but does not provide concrete steps for evaluating the progress of specific changes.

ADKAR model likely combines both Kotter's and & 7S model, by having step-by-step change implementation and highlighting where the area to improve. his model will then be used to assess the current organizational conditions and evaluate the necessary activities to ensure the success of the change process. Nevertheless, after doing gap analysis the proposed business solution will also address 7 keys changing elements, as mentioned by McKinsey.

Therefore, this research will evaluate potential issues arising from the current organizational condition. The study will explore the requirements for each division concerning organization structure, technology/ hardware, business process and job description, and people needed as the transformation progresses. In parallel, the researcher will evaluate the organization's current state, which will also involve assessing the organization's readiness for change.

Figure 7. Conceptual Framework for Initiating Strategic Change

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study constitutes a case study analysis exploring the planning for change implemented by BPM. Problem identification begins with perceived opportunities, conceptualized as innovative ideas through functional management, enabling related diversification. Therefore, the organization needs to analyze the current organizational state to understand how change effectiveness can be achieved. The researcher will collect data from organizational elements using the interview method. Subsequently, the interview manuscript results will be interpreted and classified into aspects referencing project and change management.

After completing the interpretation of interview data, the researcher will summarize a general overview of the business solution to be adopted by BPM. Then, the researcher will determine the selected strategy from various organizational development data documented by BPM. However, BPM may create new materials that have never been seen before, which will be presented in the discussion section. All steps outlined in the strategy to adopt will address the problem formulation in the first point.

The needs analysis will be prepared thoroughly, and feedback must be received from BPM's stakeholders. Subsequently, the researcher will design a detailed long-term plan tailored to the organization's capabilities and development. The researcher will also formulate documentation to track the progress of the change. Thus, the following user can continue or leverage the shift towards the next change initiative.

Figure 8. Research Design for Integrated Drilling Concept

FINDINGS AND BUSINESS SOLUTION

The primary objective of this project is to diversify BPM's business portfolio by introducing non-rig services to deliver comprehensive end-to-end well drilling services. The main objective of this project is to improve operational efficiency, optimize the use of assets, and strengthen BPM's position in the market by offering a more comprehensive and integrated service. This expansion is strategically aligned with the goal of doubling BPM's growth, targeting an increase in revenue streams and market share.

The project starts with the development of non-rig services, comprising the acquisition of new equipment and technology, personnel training and coaching for specialized abilities, and improvements to operational processes to fit with the current services. The project is scheduled to span one year, with a budget encompassing investment cost, equipment purchase, training, and associated operations expenses. Key activities within the project scope include needs analysis, service development, testing, and full implementation of the non-rig services. Offering integrated drilling services can expand the market, improving asset productivity since all rigs will be equipped with their own associated drilling package.

PROJECT MILESTONES

A. Implementation

Drilling operations refer to the process of making a well to access and extract oil and gas resources, then used to explore and produce hydrocarbon reserves. End-to-end or full cycle drilling involves several steps, including selecting and preparing a drilling site, installing rig and equipment, drilling the wellbore, until installing production system. The completed well is ready to produce oil or gas when delivered to the client.

Due to company capability, BPM started with a "partial" integrated drilling, with the scope of 6 project sets and partial services, which consisted of the rig, directional drilling, cementing and drilling fluid services. This project was executed as an intermediate target in parallel with preparing full scope transformation.

B. Changed Elements

Following the conceptual framework and the research design, four transformation elements are being adapted to the requirements of the integrated drilling project.

Restructure Organization: In order to add non-rig functions and drilling project coordinator within the Directorate Operation, the organization is then modified as follows:

Figure 9. Reorganization to Adapt Integrated Drilling Transformation

Technology and Equipment: BPM must reinforce assets and technological ability to support the overall drilling project. They should do many investments especially for non-rig services such as pumping unit, drilling fluid laboratories, etc. In the case of the investment cannot be done on time, working with partners (subcontracted) becomes temporary solution. As an alternative, this partnership scheme must be limited by time, two years maximum.

People Competency: Once the project kicks off, people knowledge enhancement must be performed. This includes upskilling all project teams and staffing the vacant. Several technical trainings are different from rig operation, such as well control, cementing practices, well architecture optimization, drilling fluid formulation, etc. Recruiting fresh graduates and then training them should be considered as long-term program for the workforce.

Tasks: To adapt to the new business strategy and integrate the latest business stream and the new organization, job description and business process must be evaluated to have proper RASCI and support integrated drilling needs.

CHANGE PROCESS

Aligning with the ADKAR model, the sequence of activities undertaken to support BPM in achieving its objectives. This process provides a comprehensive understanding of the change management processes.

- Town hall meeting gathers all BPM employees, from front-line staff to top leadership. This event aims to convey critical information regarding the vision of integrated drilling and the rationale behind the upcoming changes. It allows top leaders to share their vision, outline the business potential they foresee for the organization, and reassure all members that the changes are being made for the common good. This meeting targets employees' awareness and engagement on the nature of the change, its reasons, and the risks of not implementing it.
- Once all employees are convinced of the integrated drilling idea, surveys are taken to measure their willingness and motivation, their knowledge and their ability to embrace the change and support the integrated drilling concept. The survey employed open-ended questions, allowing respondents to provide answers in either paragraph or concise sentence formats.
- Reinforcement is the final and most critical element in ensuring the success and sustainability of transformation as a new organizational culture. Reinforcement involves internal and external factors that sustain the change. Externally, it includes recognition, rewards, and celebrations of change achievements. Internally, it refers to the personal satisfaction uniquely experienced by individuals regarding the accomplishments or personal benefits derived from successful change. Reinforcement cannot occur without the ability to perform, as individuals can only acknowledge and appreciate what has been achieved.

RESULT: INTEGRATED WELL PROJECT

After a year of project preparation, including engagement with internal and external (client) stakeholders, an integrated well-drilling project has been awarded to BPM. This project is considered successful, both operational and financial. It also brings confidence to the company and captures many lessons learned for future improvement.

A. Project Description

The project scope bundles several services, including rigs, directional drilling services, cementing services, drilling fluid services, well engineering and supervisory services. When the client asks to drill a well, the project team designs and then drills the well in collaboration with other services. BPM's company man supervises the whole drilling operation till the well is completed. The first well under this contract commenced in mid-2024.

B. Project Performance

The project is still ongoing and promising. Several achievements can be summarised below:

- operations conducted safely, no incident happened and with low non-productive time (NPT)
- overall asset productivity increased by 90%, compared to the average 60% rig productivity in individual contracts
- revenue doubled, compared to rig service only
- overall NPM of 7%, compared to 4% NPM for conventional rig service

In addition to the above positive performance, the client was satisfied due to faster delivery. This integrated well project was performed efficiently, resulting in the overall project cost paid by the client being 20% cheaper than budget; thus, more wells can be drilled.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

To have BPM's double growth by transformation to integrated drilling company, variety of approaches such as literature review, doing survey, analyzing qualitative and quantitative data, and coming up with the proposed implementation to produce conclusion and recommendation.

CONCLUSION

In responding the research objectives presented at the beginning of this paper, this research can be concluded as follows:

- The change initiative in BPM is transforming from a rig contractor to an integrated drilling company. It is successfully performed using ADKAR approach and targeting four elements to change. The change process was conducted around one year prior implementation.
- Due to the company's limitations, the business transformation started with a partially integrated drilling project in parallel with preparing the full scope.
- Implementation of this (partial) integrated drilling project demonstrates an effective change process and success in achieving targeted growth.

RECOMMENDATION

According to survey analysis and postmortem of the partial integrated drilling implementation, the recommendation for future fullscope implementation is as follows:

- BPM's transformation shows operational success but reveals reinforcement gaps. While employees have adapted well functionally, the organization now requires strategic enhancements in two key areas: career path architecture, performance measurement and incentive scheme.
- Utilization of the ADKAR framework is efficient in managing complex transformations. Subsequent studies may employ this analytical framework to further validate the ADKAR Model's efficacy in diverse business environments and organizational contexts, potentially expanding its theoretical and practical applications.

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